

Characterization of regulatory differences in ambulatory blood pressure monitoring data by means of fractal analysis

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Non-invasive wearable 24-hour ambulatory blood pressure monitoring (ABPM) devices are widely used in clinical practice and allow measuring of systolic and diastolic blood pressure (BP) time series in freely moving subjects. Complex system such as hemodynamics is demonstrated to be a self-similar hierarchy. The aim of the study is to determine the clinical potential of fractal analysis of ABPM data, in particular the fractal dimension (FD) as a quantitative measure of the chaotic component of the hemodynamics. The FD estimator and linear regression modeling (LRBPP, Linear Regression of BP Parameters) were applied on ABPM data of 57 healthy volunteers, 47 hypertensive patients and 25 patients with acute hypotensive episodes caused by various diseases. The fractal analysis of ABPM data of normotensive, hypertensive and hypotensive patients showed that all ABPM time series demonstrate antipersistence and a tendency to return to the average BP level. It was shown, if FD value of the patient's systolic blood pressure is greater or less than $FD_n = 1.8$ (characteristic of normal hemodynamics, H2-class by LRBPP), then it is associated with pathology and worsening of the patient's hemodynamic status, regardless of the disease. A decrease in the complexity of ABPM BP series (a decrease in FD values corresponding to hypotensive D1-class on LRBPP) indicates to weakened/absent regulatory influence of the BP level; an increase in FD to $FD_u = 2.0$ indicates on the correlated or quasi-periodic behavior of the ABPM BP series caused by extreme regulatory impact (hypertensive H3-class). Thus, the FD value of ABPM data can be a hemodynamic marker of the regulatory differences due to process of adaptation, self-organization, and relationship of regulatory structures of different levels. FD value and an individual hemodynamic class determined by LRBPP can use as an integral indicator of ABPM data for assess the physiological/pathological state of the patient's blood circulation.

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1. Introduction

The development of nonlinear and fractal analysis of ambulatory blood pressure monitoring (ABPM) data is of great interest due to the evidence that not only the average blood pressure (BP), but BP variability is associated with the state of the patient's cardiovascular

and autonomic nervous systems [1-4]. The BP and heart rate are not constant over any time period, but fluctuate in a complex manner, moreover the patterns of non-periodic fluctuations are determined by the interaction of external and internal environment. It has been proven [1-5], that long-term variability of cardiovascular signals (BP variability and HRV - heart rate variability) determines the self-organization and adaptation of a living organism, as well as the interaction of the regulatory structures at different levels. In

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this context, fractal and nonlinear analysis of biomedical signals are effective for understanding the complexity of the cardiac system, since the cardiac signal exhibits scale-invariant features of self-similarity (correlation, memory), whereas the underlying dynamics is nonlinear and "driven" by deterministic chaos [1-5].

Ambulatory ABPM devices measure the 20-40 samples of BP per daytime at 20-30 min measurement intervals. In practice, due to the short sample length, the analysis of BP time series is carried out by traditional methods [6] - average values, variability index, ambulatory arterial stiffness index (AASI) in linear regression modeling [7], and other highly effective diagnostics indexes.

Previously, we developed a method of linear regression analysis of ABPM (LRBPP, Linear Regression of BP Parameters) for classification of hemodynamic classes and phenotypes by individual regression coefficients of the patient's ABPM signal, namely a dependency systolic BP on pulse pressure. The LRBPP of ABPM data defines three hemodynamic phenotypes namely normotension, hypotension and hypertension (including latent hypertension), and ten hemodynamic classes accounted BP level [8-15]. Thus, in medical practice the LRBPP-analysis of ABPM allows to classify the individual hemodynamics of a patient (physiological, dysfunctional), which have clinical significance [8],[14],[15].

As noted above, physiological processes and structures of a living organism (heart rhythm, neural networks of the cerebral cortex, structure of the vascular bed, tumor growth, blood circulation model in vitro, etc.) demonstrate the fundamental property of fractality or an approximate self-similarity at different scales or time intervals for a fractal time series [16],[17]. The fractality of the cardiac signal, represented by HRV and BP variability, is due to random processes, the influence of external factors and internal regulatory humoral and nervous mechanisms (autonomic and central nervous systems) [1-4]. In general, the irregularity of

fractal biological structures is a key feature of a living organism, which determines resistance to damage and adaptive response to changes in the external environment. It is known [3], that the heart rhythm becomes more regular with aging and illness, while the organism's adaptive potential decreases. On the other hand, a high degree of chaotic heart rhythm with increasing irregular fluctuations is also a dangerous pathology.

Thus, irregularity and unpredictability are reliable characteristics of health, and a decrease in variability and the emergence of pronounced periodicity can serve as markers or early harbingers of existing or progressing pathology [3]. Therefore, in addition to traditional mathematical analysis that studies the linear properties of the cardiac signal, it is advisable to use nonlinear and fractal methods of analysis that quantitatively assess the chaos of the signal and the fractality of biological structures and processes. Therefore, along with the traditional mathematical analysis of the linear properties of the cardiac signal, it is necessary to apply nonlinear and fractal methods of analysis that quantitatively assess the chaos of the signal and the fractality of biological structures and processes.

The purpose of this study is to consider the prospects for using fractal analysis of ABPM time series to assess pathological or normal state of blood circulation in clinical practice and to determine the correspondence of the fractal dimension (FD) to the hemodynamic class determined by the results of LRBPP analysis of the patient's ABPM data. A separate task was to estimate the accuracy of FD calculation for ultra-short ABPM series of 18 measurements and above.

2. Materials and methods

A total of 129 ABPM daytime series obtained from 57 healthy volunteers and 47 hypertensive patients were analyzed [own data,

blood pressure monitoring devices BPLab, Russia] and 25 patients in the intensive care unit with secondary hypotension and severe cardiovascular disease (myocardial infarction, stroke, trauma, etc.) [PhysioNet database, <https://www.physionet.org>]. The daytime period of the ABPM time series was selected to exclude the nighttime decrease in BP levels.

At the first stage, linear regression modeling of ABPM, classification of the hemodynamic state and determination of the phenotype of each patient according to the diagnostic nomogram were carried out, and 57 healthy volunteers with a hemodynamic class H2 as a sample (model) of normal blood circulation took part in a subsequent study. Patients with pathological blood circulation were represented by classes D1 (hypotension of dysfunctional diastolic phenotype), D3 and H3, (hypertension of dysfunctional diastolic phenotype and hypertension of the harmonic phenotype). At the second stage, we performed a fractal analysis of ABPM of patients of each hemodynamic class H2, D1, D3, H3. The value of the fractal dimension FD was determined separately for the time series of the systolic (SBP), diastolic (DBP) and mean blood pressure (MBP), calculated by Hickam formula (Section 3).

3. Fractality of physiological processes

Fractals are sets of points in Euclidean space that have a fractional metric dimension different from the topological one (in the sense of Minkowski or Hausdorff). The concept of fractality as a model is used if a real physiological object with non-linear dependencies and non-deterministic behavior cannot be represented by the classical models (trend, regression, etc.), which assume that the future is quite deterministic. On the contrary, the fractality of a physiological object implies a multiplicity of options and states. Fractal analysis of

medical signals cannot be performed without a priori model that has essential features of the physiological process. The fractional Brownian motion (fBm) is the main fractal model for human biosignals, fBm demonstrates the long-term memory, when the future of a process is determined by its past with a waning influence (the variance of the increments indicates the power-law scaling) [16],[17].

The fractality of physiological signals is different for monofractal processes (self-similar processes with a single scaling exponent) and multifractal processes (spectrum of exponents and complex behavior). The self-similarity parameter of monofractals is the Hurst exponent (H) in the range [0 1], which is a critical measure of the long-term correlation of the stochastic process: range $0.5 < H < 1$ indicates that the process has long-range correlation and trends; value $H = 0.5$ means the process is a random Wiener process (classical Brownian motion); the range $0 < H < 0.5$ indicates an antipersistent (anticorrelated) fBm process.

However, for reliable estimation of the H the stationary set of several thousand measurements are required [17]. It is obvious that physiological processes of this scale repeatedly change the behavior, therefore, researchers are considering methods for determining the local FD of data.

FD values indicate how densely a metric space is occupied by a fractal set [16],[17]. It is known, that the Hausdorff dimension of a fractal set is greater than the topological dimension and determined by the expression:

$$FD = -\lim_{r \rightarrow 0} \frac{\ln(N_r)}{\ln(r)}, \quad (1)$$

N_r is the minimum number of spheres of radius r required to cover the area of the object. For a fractal set, the power dependence of the number of structural elements on their size is satisfied: $N = N_0 r^{-FD}$, where FD is the fractal dimension. The power law is a characteristic property and a mathematical expression of the self-similarity of fBm. However, the self-similarity of physiological time series (as well as all natural

fractals) is observed only in a finite range of scales, beyond which fractal properties are absent, so the limit in the theoretical definition of FD does not make sense. In this case, FD is defined on scales where the time series exhibit fractal behavior. Let us consider a time series of BP values, which presumably consists of quasi-periodic and random oscillations, as well as fractal structures with the scaling property. In particular, ABPM is a discrete time series of systolic BP (SBP) and diastolic BP (DBP) as a function of measurement time: $SBP = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_N\}$ and $DBP = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_N\}$ with the amplitude determined for the current measurement index. Since the index increases linearly from 1 to N (an amplitude is the fractal variable), it is assumed that the SBP and DBP are one-dimensional fractal sets, FD of which is within $[1, 2]$, and the Hurst exponent is given by the relation: $H = 2 - FD$ [16],[17].

The main problem of reliable FD estimation is the short length of ABPM time series, because short signal becomes more similar to a random data set [18]. It is obvious that the fractality of the process does not change with a reduction in the measurement frequency, but the uncertainty of the value of FD increases. Therefore, we considered various methods, suitable for non-stationary or short ABPM time series: Higuchi algorithm [19] and the least coverage method [2], [16]. Higuchi algorithm is widely used for non-stationary series due to algorithmic approximation. The least covering method uses an algorithm for averaging the local FD dimensions in sliding windows with a width multiple of the measurement interval (here - 20 min) and a height specified by the difference between the maximum and minimum values of the signal amplitude in the window.

The mathematical expression for the local FD of the SBP by this method is determined by the formula:

$$FDl = \frac{\log(N-1)}{\log(N-1) + \log(\frac{d}{L})}, \quad (2)$$

$$d = \max\{s_i\} - \min\{s_i\}, \quad (3)$$

$$L = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} |s_{i+1} - s_i|, \quad (4)$$

where N is the width and i is the number of the current window on the SBP time series. FD of the entire series is estimated as the median of the local values. Due to importance of correct FD estimation for ultrashort ABPM data, we applied the above algorithms to set of 100 artificial fBm of length $N = 18$ with known theoretical FD between 1 and 2 with a step of 0.1 (black diagonal in Figure 1). The FD values by the least coverage method (black circles in Figure 1) are almost the same as the theoretical values compared to FD using the Higuchi method (gray circles in Figure 1). Thus, the absolute error of the least coverage method was smaller, so this algorithm was used to analyze ABPM time series of 18-40 measurements.

FIG. 1. Efficiency of two algorithms for calculating FD, using the averaged results of ultrashort artificial fBm. The theoretical FD for fBm are on the diagonal.

4. Results

At the first stage, the LRBPP was used to determine the hemodynamic class based on daytime ABPM data of 57 healthy volunteers (all patients were represented by the normotensive harmonic H2-class), 47 hypertensive patients (patients were represented by 2 classes: hypertensive harmonic H3-class and hypertensive diastolic D3-class) and 25 patients of intensive care department with secondary hypotension caused by different severe diseases (hypotensive diastolic D1-class) [PhysioNet database, <https://www.physionet.org>]. At the second stage, for ABPM of patients of D1, D3, H2, H3-classes the FD value was determined for SBP, DBP and mean blood pressure (MBP, Hickam's formula); the duration of the daytime ABPM was 18-40 measurements, Figure 2.

Figure 2 shows significant differences ($p < 0.05$) for SBP of patients with the harmonic circulation phenotype (H2- and H3-class) compared to patients with the dysfunctional diastolic circulation phenotype (D1- and D3-class). Therefore, we considered FD for SBP time series as a marker of regulatory hemodynamic differences.

Figure 2 also shows a tendency for FD to increase for the hypertensive harmonic H3-class compared to the normotensive harmonic H2-class (norm), which is associated with a change in normal physiological reactions caused by the enlarged cardiovascular control. In this case, the SBP exhibits a more correlated or periodic behavior, similar to that described in [20] for the HRV of patients with a number of cardiac pathologies.

An opposite example is the loss of fractal dynamics (complexity of ABPM) and a decrease in FD values for the hypotensive dysfunctional diastolic D1-class, whose cardiac signals are characterized by pronounced chaotic behavior due to a decrease (or complete absence) of cardiovascular control. We observed this phenomenon in a patient with a transplanted heart, represented

by the normotensive harmonic H2-class, but $FD=1.6$ (sample B009SB, EuroBavar, <http://www.eurobavar.altervista.org/>). This sample demonstrates, that hemodynamics goes beyond the linear model, namely there is the discrepancy between the qualitative variable (normotensive harmonic H2-class) and the numerical value of FD (low value, which is characteristic of the diastolic phenotype).

FIG. 2. FD of SBP, DBP and MBP time series in 4 hemodynamic classes. * $p < 0.05$, statistically significant differences between harmonic (H2-, H3-class) and dysfunctional diastolic (D1-, D3-class) types of blood circulation

In the clinical aspect, patients of both hemodynamic D1- and H3-classes have pathological hemodynamics, but with diametrically opposite effects of regulatory systems on BP level and the magnitude of the adaptive potential.

5. Fractal dimension of systolic blood pressure as a marker of the hemodynamic control of blood pressure

In this paper, the FD value of SBP is considered as a systemic regulation marker of BP level, Figures 2, 3.

Analysis of clinical ABPM data showed that FD value for SBP is limited from below by

FIG. 3. (Color online) Left - FD of SBP. Right - correlation properties of SBP and the alleged adaptation state.

the threshold of $FDd=1.5$ (random dynamics, minimal complexity of SBP, weakened or absent regulatory control of BP, the cardiovascular system is poorly adapted to stress in everyday life). Low FD values are typical for pathological states of patients in D1-class (patients in the intensive care unit with severe cardiovascular lesions and secondary hypotension).

The area of self-similar (fractal) dynamics of SBP is associated with the value of $FDn \sim 1.8$ (balance of neurohumoral regulation of BP, maximum complexity of SBP time series), this FD value corresponds to the hemodynamics of healthy patients in H2-class with a high degree of adaptability of the cardiovascular system.

An increase in FD to the upper threshold value $FDu=2.0$ (fully correlated SBP time series, strong cardiovascular regulation of BP, weak adaptation to stress in everyday life) is typical for hypertensive patients with harmonious circulation (H3-class).

It should be noted that the FD values for all hemodynamic classes exceed the lower threshold $FDd=1.5$, therefore, all ABPM are antipersistent. In other words, daytime ABPM data are quite predictable and exhibit negative long-range correlation (the increments of the BP are likely to be followed by decreases and vice versa) [21].

6. Conclusion

The non-invasive, inexpensive and widely used ABPM devices are typically programmed to record BP at 20 - 30 min intervals over a defined period. LRBPP model is relatively simple to describe ABPM time series, that has advantages over other approaches due to interpretability and the ability to classify the hemodynamic state. However, linear regression modeling can have significant drawbacks when the linearity assumption is a poor or incorrect approximation.

Considering the multidirectional and balanced influence of the sympathetic and parasympathetic branches of the autonomic nervous system, as well as hormonal and other factors on BP, we propose an integral indicator of hemodynamic state and adaptation, consisting of the fractal dimension value and a qualitative variable - the individual hemodynamic class, determined by LRBPP of ABPM. Moreover, fractal analysis is probably the only method of nonlinear dynamics that quantitatively evaluates the chaotic component of hemodynamics of ultrashort ABPM time series.

The study showed the comparability of the results of ABPM analysis and clinical interpretation of two methods of assessing blood circulation - determination of the hemodynamic phenotype and class by LRBPP method and fractal analysis. Thus, the value of the fractal dimension is a nonlinear parameter that not only confirms the existence of harmonic and diastolic hemodynamic phenotypes, but also determines the patient's adaptive capacity and the influence of regulatory mechanisms on the BP level. At the same time, the fractality of biomedical signals practically has not been studied in the clinical medicine, but the clinical significance of hemodynamic phenotypes and classes has been confirmed by a number of published studies [8],[14],[15].

Our results prove that all clinical samples, regardless of the hemodynamic class, demonstrate antipersistence with a tendency to return to average BP values. Short ABPM series are

characterized by the Hurst exponent within $0 < H < 0.5$, while the fractal dimension exceeds the critical value $FDd=1.5$, separating persistent and antipersistent behavior of ABPM time series.

It is shown, if FD value of the patient's SBP is greater or less than $FDn \sim 1.8$, which is characteristic of normal hemodynamics, then this deviation is associated with pathology, and most likely worse prognosis for the patient, regardless of the disease. A decrease in the complexity of the ABPM and a decrease in FD values correspond to states with weakened (absent) regulatory mechanisms for BP level. On the other hand, an

increase in FD values to $FDu=2.0$ indicates on correlated or quasi-periodic behavior of ABPM, probably due to excessive regulatory influence of the nervous system. The latter may be a harbinger of the depletion of the adaptive mechanisms.

In this way the fundamental property of complex biological systems, consisting in the exclusion of states with high order or complete chaos, is confirmed. Therefore, the FD of ABPM time series recorded by outpatient devices can be used as a nonlinear diagnostic marker of the hemodynamic state and adaptation.

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